

Milestone:

MS37 - Third Stakeholders forum - Stakeholder forum newsletter produced

Lead Participant:

ELIXIR Hub

Author:**Due:**

September 2025

Date Of Completion:

16 February 2026

Means of Verification

A special issue of the GDI newsletter with a short summary, the presentation slides of the Stakeholders Forum was sent to 320 subscribers on 16 February 2026. ([Link to the newsletter preview](#))

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

The newsletter was delayed as the Stakeholder Forum was held in January 2026.

Project participants & others

Zippy Tseng (ELIXIR Hub)
Elaine Harrison (ELIXIR Hub)
Melissa Konopko (ELIXIR Hub)
Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)
Ellie Younger (ELIXIR Hub)

Next action steps

- Promote the GDI newsletter on social media platforms.
- Share the Stakeholders Forum summary report in the next regular newsletter after MB review.
- Maintain the GDI newsletter with quarterly updates and annual special issue after the GDI Stakeholder Forum.

